

ENVIRONMENTAL AIR SAMPLING FOR DETECTION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF AIRBORNE MICROORGANISMS

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ABSTRACT

Every day, numerous patients and healthy individuals visit the compact surroundings of a tertiary care tuberculosis hospital in Delhi. Assessing the air quality of airborne *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* is crucial for controlling its nosocomial transmission. In this proof-of-concept study, environmental air sampling was employed to detect and characterize *M. tuberculosis* at the institute. Using an Envirotech APM 414 air sampler, air samples were collected from 14 different sites within the hospital. Three methods were employed for trapping airborne organisms: filter paper, 7H9 liquid broth, and deionized water. The 7H9 broth was directly incubated for the isolation and identification of mycobacteria, while the filter paper and deionized water samples were processed via the modified Petroff method and subsequently cultured on various media, including 7H9 broth, Lowenstein–Jensen (LJ) medium, Sabouraud dextrose agar, and blood agar. Airborne organisms were detected at 12 of the 14 sampled sites. The two sites where no organisms were detected were mechanically ventilated, negative pressure multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) wards. *Mycobacterium chelonae* was isolated from two naturally ventilated wards. In total, four bacterial species, one mycobacterial species, and one fungal species were identified. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most commonly isolated bacterial species, and *Aspergillus fumigatus* was the only fungal species identified. This study highlights that hospital environments are not free from airborne contamination by mycobacteria, bacteria, or fungi. Droplet nuclei can remain suspended in the air for extended periods, posing a continuous risk of infection. Negative pressure wards were found to be safer than naturally ventilated wards, underscoring the need for improved indoor air quality in hospital settings.

Keywords: Environmental sampling, airborne organisms, impingers, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, cross-sectional.

INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) remains one of the leading causes of death globally and has afflicted humankind for more than 3000 years [1]. In 2023, tuberculosis likely regained its position as the world's leading cause of death from a single infectious agent after being surpassed by coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) for three years [2]. It is estimated that *Mtb* infects

approximately one quarter of the world's population. Despite its widespread prevalence, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* can remain dormant in the body, leading to latent TB infections that can persist for a lifetime without causing symptoms. Over 90% of individuals who develop symptomatic tuberculosis are adults, with a higher incidence observed in men than in women. By 2023, it was estimated that 10.8 million people worldwide were infected with TB, resulting in more than 1.25 million deaths. The World Health Organization (WHO) reported that in 2024, India had the highest burden of TB (26%), with an alarming rate of approximately two TB-related deaths every three minutes [3].

India is the most populous country in the world, with an estimated 1.432 billion inhabitants (<https://worldpopulationreview.com/>). Its capital is the second most populous city globally (after Tokyo, Japan), with approximately 36.1 million residents and a growth rate of 2.73% (<https://www.un.org/development/desa/pd/>). Delhi shares borders with Uttar Pradesh, which has over 241 million inhabitants, and Haryana, which has a population of approximately 25 million. Tuberculosis, also known as Koch's disease, is transmitted primarily from active infected patients (hosts) to healthy individuals (recipients) through the dispersal of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb)-laden droplets or aerosols, most often infecting the lungs, leading to pulmonary TB. A single cough or sneeze can release up to 40,000 droplets, and the infectious dose of tuberculosis is very low (fewer than 10 bacteria); therefore, each droplet has the potential to transmit infection [4,5]. The National Institute of Tuberculosis and Respiratory Diseases (NITRD) is the apex institute in the country dedicated to the prevention, control, and treatment of tuberculosis and allied diseases. Approximately 50,000 patients from local and other states visit the outpatient department (OPD) annually, and approximately 6,000 patients are admitted to wards each year.

Airborne pathogens in hospital premises pose a significant health concern for hospital workers, patients' companions, and healthy individuals attending the OPD. In this context, a study conducted in the 1950s involving guinea pigs aimed to ascertain the transmission of diseases through the air [6]. Many airborne diseases spread when an infected patient coughs or sneezes, releasing droplet nuclei into the air. These floating droplet nuclei can travel considerable distances, survive in the air for prolonged periods, and infect susceptible individuals [7,8]. Despite ongoing robust TB control programs, the number of reported cases of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb) continues to rise globally.

Understanding the transmissibility and infectivity of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* remains imprecise. Rapid urbanization and the construction of new compact infrastructures in TB hospitals, where the same air circulates in areas, may contribute to the increased incidence of tuberculosis [9,10]. Hospital vicinities and other healthcare facilities require adequate ventilation, patient comfort, and control of hazardous emissions [11]. Moreover, the biological quality of air in hospital environments is particularly concerning, as patients can transmit pathogenic microorganisms via air to staff, visitors, and companions [12,13].

This study was conducted to assess and evaluate the air quality in the indoor environments of the ICU, laboratory microscopic room, and culture/drug susceptibility testing (DST) room. The data collected may be used to establish standards for acceptable microbial populations and to propose suitable guidelines to reduce the proportion of microbes in indoor air.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted from October 03, 2018, to August 30, 2019, at a tertiary care respiratory hospital. The hospital has an international microbiology laboratory with a national reference laboratory for culture/DST for mycobacteriology. To prevent the transmission of tuberculosis, all staff members and patients are required to wear surgical masks, even in the OPD area. In this study, 14 different sites were selected within the hospital premises, covering MDR-TB wards, general TB wards, OPD consultation rooms, and the laboratory of the National Institute of Tuberculosis and Respiratory Diseases (formerly known as the Lala Ram Sarup Institute of Tuberculosis and Respiratory Diseases) in New Delhi, India (Table 1).

The two MDR-TB wards were equipped with mechanically ventilated negative pressure rooms, where the air flowed through high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filters. In contrast, the general wards were naturally ventilated, with air flowing from one direction to another through windows placed at each end. At each location, three air samples were collected for two hours in the morning, between 11 AM and 1 PM. Air samples were taken from these sites by rotation at fixed time intervals to cover peak working hours. Air sampling sites were randomly selected, and samples were collected via an Envirotech APM 414 air sampler (Envirotech Instruments Private Limited, Delhi, India). The two-hour sampling duration was arbitrarily chosen to ensure that the air samples could be collected and processed on the same day. The Envirotech APM 414 consists of three connected components: an air-sucking plunger covered with sterilized filter paper (Whatman GF/A, pore size of 1.6 μm), a steel case containing three glass impingers, and a constant flow pump (HFS-113A, Gillan). A constant flow pump was used to draw air from the environment, passing it through filter paper and impingers to trap airborne organisms.

Collection of air samples

Air samples were collected from October 03, 2018, to March 15, 2019, via an Envirotech APM 414 air sampler. During the collection process, air enters through the plunger of the sampler, where a Whatman filter (pore size of 1.6 μm) is placed, and then passes through three glass impingers fitted with steel. The air flow rate was maintained between 10–12 liters per minute (L/min) (Picture-1).

Among the three glass impingers, two contained 8 ml of 7H9 broth, and the third impinger contained 40 ml of sterilized deionized water. The total volume of air aspirated onto the filter paper and into the impingers containing 7H9 broth and deionized water ranged from 1200 to 1440 liters of air per sample from each location (Picture2). The air sampler was set up at approximately 1.5 meters above floor level, corresponding to the bed height (Fig.1). To determine the bacterial load in the air, the exposed filter paper and the air-charged liquid medium from the impingers were further processed.

Picture-1: Collection of air samples

Picture-2: Collection of air samples

Figure-1: Schematic representation of sample collection

Processing of filter paper

Following the collection of air samples, the exposed filter paper was immediately immersed in peptone broth (Hi-Media Laboratories Limited, Mumbai, India). The peptone broth was then processed via the modified Petroff method. Deposits from the broth were inoculated into different culture media for the identification and isolation of mycobacterial, bacterial, and fungal organisms.

Processing of impinger tubes

The contents of the impingers were transferred into 50 ml Falcon tubes. The two Falcon tubes containing 7H9 broth (Hi-Media) were directly incubated in a shaking incubator at 37°C for six weeks. The third Falcon tube containing deionized water was processed separately. This Falcon tube was centrifuged at $8600 \times g$ at 4°C for 15 minutes. The sediment was then resuspended in 5 ml of sterile deionized water and divided into two parts. The first part was decontaminated via the modified Petroff method, and the deposit was inoculated into solid and liquid mycobacterial culture media. Specifically, 50 μl of the deposit was inoculated into Lowenstein–Jensen (LJ) media supplemented with glycerol, and 500 μl was inoculated into

Middlebrook 7H9 broth supplemented with growth supplement and PANTA (Becton & Dickinson). Both mediums were incubated at 37°C for six weeks in a shaking incubator.

For the isolation and identification of bacterial organisms, the second part of the processed samples was inoculated into nutrient agar (Hi-Media) supplemented with 100 mg/L cycloheximide (Hi-Media) for sampling and cultivating bacteria. For the isolation of fungi, Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) (Hi-Media) supplemented with 10 mg/L chloramphenicol was used. Two plates of each medium were used to isolate bacteria and fungi. Nutrient agar and blood agar plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 hours to allow the growth of aerobic bacteria, whereas SDA plates were incubated for up to three weeks at 25°C and 37°C to allow the growth of fungal colonies. Once growth was detected, it was confirmed by Ziehl–Neelsen (ZN) staining and Gram staining. Mycobacterium growth was further confirmed at the species level via conventional biochemical tests, including the niacin test, nitrate reduction test, heat-resistant catalase test (HRCT), and para-nitrobenzoic acid (PNB) test. Growth on nutrient agar, blood agar, and SDA agar was further tested for the presence of pyogenic bacteria and fungi [14].

RESULTS

During the study period, air samples were collected in two cycles during the first half of the working hours, specifically from 11 AM to 1 PM. The first cycle commenced on October 03, 2018, and ended on November 30, 2018. The second cycle began on January 28, 2019, and ended on March 15, 2019 (Table 1). The air quality of the premises was monitored for a total of 56 hours throughout the study. The total volume of air sampled in each cycle ranged from 33,600 to 40,320 liters during the 56 hours of air sample collection. By covering 14 different sites, we aimed to include all vital locations within the hospital premises where the bacterial load would likely be the highest. Air samples were collected during peak hours of activity throughout the hospital.

The dates and times were selected to ensure that the hospital premises had the maximum number of patients and their attendants. In the wards, air samples were collected while patients were on bed, and their coughing activity was continuously observed during this period. During the 2-hour collection duration, each patient coughed at least 10–12 times, producing aerosols. Additionally, the activity around the patients' beds was monitored, revealing that three to four hospital personnel visited the patients' bedside for various reasons.

Microorganisms were found at 12 out of the 14 sites. In the two negative-pressure MDR-TB wards (ward-1 and ward-2), no organisms were detected. In ward 3, *Aspergillus fumigatus* was isolated during the first cycle, but no organisms were found in the second cycle. *Mycobacterium chelonae* and *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) were detected in both cycles in ward 4, whereas in ward 6, *Staphylococcus aureus* was consistently found. In ward 9, both *Mycobacterium chelonae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were identified in both cycles. In the intensive care unit, *Staphylococcus aureus* was detected in both cycles, and coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) were detected only during the second cycle, whereas in the smear microscopy room, both *Staphylococcus aureus* and CoNS were present in both cycles. The culture/DST room contained *S. aureus* in the first cycle and both *S. aureus* and *K. pneumoniae* in the second cycle. In the outpatient consultation rooms, room 101 had

Escherichia coli in the first round and *Citrobacter freundii* in the second round. In room 102, which was designated for ART consulting, *Staphylococcus aureus* was found in the first cycle, and *Micrococcus* spp. were found in the second cycle. Room 104 consistently had CoNS in both rounds. Room 108 showed the presence of both *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in both rounds. Finally, room 110, designated for pediatric patients, had both *Staphylococcus aureus* and coagulase-negative staphylococci in both rounds of sample collection.

This study identified six different bacterial organisms, along with one fungal species and one mycobacterial species. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most prevalent bacterial organism found during air sampling. (Table 2).

Table 1: Sites of air sampling.

Sl No	Sites	Collection of air samples		Description of Site
		1 st cycle	2 nd cycle	
1.	Ward 1	03.10.2018	28.01.2019	Drug resistant TB ward with negative pressure ventilation
2.	Ward 2	08.10.2018	31.01.2019	Drug resistant TB ward with negative pressure ventilation
3.	Ward 3	11.10.2018	05.02.2019	Respiratory emergency ward
4.	Ward 4	15.10.2018	08.02.2019	Drug resistant TB ward with natural ventilation
5.	Ward 6	22.10.2018	12.02.2019	Drug resistant TB ward with natural ventilation
6.	Ward 9	26.10.2018	15.02.2019	Drug resistant TB ward with natural ventilation
7.	ICU	30.10.2018	20.02.2019	Critical patients
8.	Smear microscopy room-113	05.11.2018	23.02.2019	ZN smear examination
9.	Culture/DST room	09.11.2018	26.02.2019	Solid culture and DST
10.	OPD 101	13.11.2018	01.03.2019	Outpatient consulting room
11.	OPD 102	16.11.2018	05.03.2019	ART consulting room
12.	OPD104	21.11.2018	08.03.2019	Outpatient consulting room
13.	OPD108	26.11.2018	12.03.2019	Outpatient consulting room
14.	OPD 110	30.11.2018	15.03.2019	Outpatient consulting room for pediatric patients

Table 2: Organisms isolated from different sites.

Site	ZN smear	1 st cycle	2 nd cycle
ward 1	Negative	Nil	Nil
Ward 2	Negative	Nil	Nil
Ward 3	Negative	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	Nil
ward 4	Negative	<i>Mycobacterium chaelonae</i> , <i>staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Mycobacterium chaelonae</i> , <i>staphylococcus aureus</i>
ward 6	Negative	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
ward 9	Negative	<i>Mycobacterium chaelonae</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Mycobacterium chaelonae</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
ICU	Negative	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>CoNS</i>
Smear microscopy room -16	Negative	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Coagulase negative staph</i> ,	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>CoNS</i>
Culture/DST room no-113	Negative	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>klebsiellapneumoniae</i>
OPD 101	Negative	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>
OPD 102	Negative	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Micrococcus spp</i>
OPD104	Negative	<i>Coagulase negative staph</i>	<i>Coagulase negative staph</i>
OPD108	Negative	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>klebsiella pneumonia</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>klebsiella pneumonia</i>
OPD 110	Negative	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Coagulase negative staph</i> .	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Coagulase negative staph</i> .

DISCUSSION

For the first time, a study was initiated to check for the presence of *Mycobacterium* in the precincts of a tertiary care TB hospital in northern India. The samples collected in the mechanically ventilated negative pressure rooms in the MDR-TB ward, where the patient density was moderate and the movement of others was protected and restricted, revealed that mycobacteria were not present in the air samples. These rooms were fitted with HEPA filters, providing an average of 6–10 air changes per hour. The droplet nuclei generated by the patients were likely removed by the air handling unit.

The removal of droplet nuclei and regular replacement of fresh air were discussed in their study, which emphasized that 99.9% of airborne contaminants were cleared within 69 minutes in negative pressure rooms [15].

Simultaneously, at naturally ventilated sites, where the patient population is dense and the movements of staff and others are frequent, the presence of mycobacteria in the collected air samples was recorded. In these wards, bacteria involuntarily released into the air are not completely cleared through natural ventilation; hence, they remain suspended in the surroundings [13]. It is well documented that occupant density is a key factor affecting the concentration of airborne bacteria. A pilot study revealed that higher airborne bacterial density is observed in areas with high movement of patients and attendants, highlighting an increase in the indoor rate of airborne microorganisms when an excessive number of patients, visitors, and hospital personnel are present in designated areas [16,17].

An interesting finding observed in this study was that *Mycobacterium chelonae* was not isolated from the filter paper samples, whereas it was detected in 7H9 broth and processed deionized distilled water. A possible explanation for this is that the pore size of the Whatman filter paper allowed the organism to pass through it. As a result, when it passed through the liquid media, it became trapped and subsequently grew in the culture media. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas* were trapped in the filter paper, likely due to their relatively high concentrations in the air, which allowed them to be trapped and grow in the processed filter paper samples.

The isolation of bacterial organisms from intensive care units that address critical cases underscores the need for effective strategies to reduce the number of airborne organisms as much as possible. One species of mycobacteria grows in air samples and can cause infections in susceptible or immunocompromised people. Although it is unlikely to cause respiratory infections in healthy individuals, the magnitude of infection spread through even a single *Mycobacterium* cannot be ignored. Its impact may be substantial in susceptible and immunocompromised hosts. In many locations in this study, other bacteria were isolated and identified, potentially serving as sources of pyogenic infection for individuals in the OPD or wards. The airborne bacterial and fungal species isolated in this study from indoor air have been reported in several studies outside India via different isolation and identification procedures.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the results highlighted the presence of mycobacteria, bacterial organisms, and fungal organisms in the air as droplet nuclei across various settings, including general wards, outpatient departments (OPDs), and hospital laboratories. The air quality significantly differed between MDR-TB negative-pressure wards and MDR-TB open wards, with a notably greater presence of pyogenic bacteria in the general wards. The two nontuberculous mycobacterial strains detected in the general wards were considered normal environmental contaminants.

The results emphasize the value of air sampling technology in hospital epidemiology and infection control, especially for addressing the transmission of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb) among healthy contacts and within noninstitutional settings. This knowledge can inform the development of effective air quality policies to maintain a germ-free atmosphere in hospitals. Furthermore, in India, more than 50% of TB patients experience social stigma postdiagnosis, leading to nondisclosure and noncompliance with mask wearing in public. This

behavior poses a high risk for *M. tuberculosis* transmission in crowded areas such as markets, religious sites, and transportation hubs, particularly during festival seasons.

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Competing interests: The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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